

EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In the article, the information about the education system of Uzbekistan was briefly discussed, and the information about the education of students with mental retardation was also discussed.

Key words: Education, system, children, educational form, colleges, schools.

Inclusive education is a system of educational services based on the principle of securing children's rights to receive education, and the rights to receive it at their place of residence, which means that a child with specific educational needs is supposed to study at a general education institution. When explaining the essence of "inclusion", it's necessary to pay attention to three elements that illustrate its specific features, in particular: (a) inclusion is a process that should be considered as an ongoing search for effective ways to satisfy individual needs of children; (b)

inclusion is related to identifying obstacles and overcoming them; (c) inclusion focuses on those groups of students that are exposed to the “risk” of exclusion from the educational process or limitation of their possibility to receive education. Furthermore, the main criterion, according to which education of all schoolchildren with specific characteristics of their development shall be organized, includes full satisfaction of the educational needs of the schoolchildren.

The Social Initiatives Support Fund of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter SISF) has been implementing the project named “Inclusive Education in Uzbekistan” since 2007. The main target of the project is to create equal possibilities for obtaining education by children and teenagers with disabilities. The project “Inclusive Education in Uzbekistan” is focused on promoting the model of lifelong inclusive education in the Republic by means of its stage-by-stage implementation into the system of elementary, secondary-level, vocational training and higher education, and on creating conditions for improvement of the quality of inclusive education. Within the scope of this project a concept has been developed named “National Model of the Inclusive Education”, which is being implemented into the system of preschool and school education by means of setting up mixed groups and classes based on the pilot kindergartens and schools in Termiz, Karshi, Navoi, Samarkand, Jizzakh, Gulistan, Tashkent, Andijon, Fergana, Kokand, Urgench and Nukus. The specific feature of the national model of the

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inclusive education is that it is built up taking into account the national and foreign experience. According to SISF, more than 600 children are currently studying in the mixed groups and classes of pilot kindergartens, schools, lyceums and colleges of the above cities. In Uzbekistan, the practice of inclusive education goes back for generations. It is well known that the great scientist of the Middle Ages Al-Buhari had an impaired vision, but nevertheless, received education at a madrasah. And what is inclusive education? It is the conditions in which children, regardless of whether they find themselves in a difficult living situation, or lost their family, can receive education in the same conditions as other children. Nowadays, practically all pupils of “Mehribonlik” orphan homes are studying at the general education schools. There are only two specialized schools at 28 orphan homes. By the way, changes are also happening in this area. Back in the old days there used to be specialized classes consisting of pupils from orphan homes, whereas, nowadays, such a practice doesn't exist any longer. Children with disabilities have the right to chose either a general education school or a specialized school. There are 86 specialized boarding schools in the Republic, and the government pays the same attention to their development as to the development of the general education schools.

That is the main difference of the Uzbekistan experience of education development from that of the experience of many foreign countries, where there were attempts

to transfer all children with disabilities to general education institutions. One of the main tasks that the government should solve is further development of inclusive education, and strengthening of the material and technical base of the educational establishments. Implementation of the project for development of education for persons with disabilities, financed by a loan of the Asian Development Bank, is a specific example of this work. Furthermore, presently governmental programs for strengthening the material and technical base of “Mehrbonlik” orphan homes and specialized boarding schools have been prepared and are now at the stage of approval. The priority area of activities of the Forum organizers, which includes the Ministry of Public Education, the “Sen Elgiz Emassan” Fund, and the Republican Center of Social Adaptation of Children provides for further generation of positive public opinion about inclusive education. Task of the teacher in inclusive education is to give children with disabilities knowledge on an equal basis with their healthy mates, and at the same time to find an individual approach to each child, taking into account his/her needs and abilities. Inclusive education is a process of development of general education which ensures the accessibility of education for everybody, including children with specific needs. Inclusive education provides for an equal attitude to all children, but at the same time creates conditions for children with specific educational needs. Thus, the main function of inclusive education is to provide successful adaptation of a child with limited

physical or mental abilities to adult life, and lack of discrimination on the part of other people.

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